

INDIRECT TRANSLATION AND INDIRECT INFLUENCE: ALOJZ GRADNIK'S SLOVENE TRANSLATIONS OF ASIAN LITERATURES

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Keywords: As is well known, non-dominant (peripheral) literary cultures often rely on translation to a greater extent than dominant (central) literary cultures that tend to be more »self-sufficient«. Among literary cultures that are translation-dependent to a high degree is also Slovene literary culture, in which translations account for about 31% of all titles published. Like many other non-dominant literary cultures, the Slovene literary culture too can be characterized by its tendency to autonomous translation (as opposed to heteronymous translation, more typically practiced in dominant cultures; cfr. Cronin 2006: 40–41), ie. to rely on its own resources both when translating from other cultures into Slovene and, to some degree at least, also when its own literature is translated into other languages. As a consequence, in a number of situations involving autonomous translation, indirect translation will be a necessity (Assis Rosa *et al.* (2017), Marin-Lacarta (2017), Washbourne (2013)).

The paper aims to present the case of Alojz Gradnik (1882-1967), an important Slovene poet and translator, whose large translation oeuvre is somewhat atypical in that he authored indirect translations from several languages (along with his many direct translations from various European languages). In the 1920s and 1930s, in the period of a significant expansion of the Slovene literary translation corpus, Gradnik produced a number of indirect translations from Chinese, Bengali and Japanese, to which he later added also translations from Persian. On the basis of published sources as well as of Gradnik's literary archive, the paper will discuss the place of indirect translations within Gradnik's oeuvre as a translator and a poet, who absorbed non-European literary influences in his own work. Further, it will examine the function of his translations of texts of non-European literatures in the construction of the corpus of literary texts in Slovene at a pivotal moment of its history.

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